

**GraspOS SCOPE+i
Resource:**

**Stakeholder
mapping
template**

**Actionable
version**

Definition

This template supports the identification and documentation of stakeholders in research assessment (RA) processes. Stakeholder mapping is critical because effective RA requires a diversity of perspectives, expertise, and experiences. The template prompts you to list stakeholders by category (e.g., researchers, HR, administration, library, funders, national bodies) and to record their roles and contributions to the process.

Relevant SCOPE stages

The template is particularly useful in the following phases:

- Start with what you value: clarify institutional values and priorities by identifying who defines them.
- Context considerations: map the environment, actors, and power dynamics that shape the RA process.

When and how to use

When:

- At the start of a research assessment process.
- When reviewing or designing assessment protocols or career development frameworks.
- During preparation of self-evaluations or strategic planning to ensure inclusivity.

How:

- Map all relevant stakeholders, grouping them into categories (e.g., researchers, management, HR, funders, bibliometricians, national stakeholders).
- Specify their roles and activities (e.g., evaluator, coordinator, data provider, reporting, decision-making).
- Use the map to check diversity of representation, avoid blind spots, and ensure all critical perspectives are included.

Guidance

- For HR and administration: ensure staff policies, recruitment, and career development stakeholders are represented.
- For researchers and managers: balance voices across disciplines, seniority levels, and demographic diversity.
- For executive leadership: recognise the influence of external stakeholders (e.g., ministries, funders, indexing services).
- For assessment coordinators: use the mapping to plan communication, define responsibilities, and distribute tasks.

Tips for effective use:

- Begin broad, then refine—missing stakeholders can undermine fairness and credibility.
- Document both formal roles (decision-making, evaluation) and informal contributions (advice, advocacy).
- Revisit and update the map throughout the RA process.

Further reading

GraspOS SCOPE+I Resources

- Guide for assembling an assessment team.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525548>

Other

- SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

